

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

Single-institution analysis of incidence of acute radiodermatitis in women with breast cancer undergoing moderate hypofractionated radiotherapy

Dušanka Tešanović¹, Jelena Ličina^{1,2}, Branislav Đuran¹, Igor Đan¹

¹Oncology Institute Vojvodine, Sremska Kamenica

²Medical Faculty of Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad

*Correspondence: Dusanka Tešanović e-mail: tesanovic.dusanka@onk.ns.ac.rs;

Objective: To estimate the incidence of acute radiodermatitis during the treatment in women with breast cancer undergoing moderate hypofractionated radiotherapy (HFRT) comparing to conventional radiotherapy (CRT) at the Oncology Institute of Vojvodina in Sremska Kamenica.

Methods: This study was observational, prospective, and longitudinal study performed at Department of Radiation Oncology at the Clinic for Radiation therapy at the Oncology Institute Vojvodine. We divided patients into two groups, 77 patients in group 1 used HFRT regimen 40 Gy in 15 fraction over three weeks and 77 patients in group 2 used CRT regimen 50 Gy in 25 fractions (+/- "boost" 14Gy/7fr) over five-six weeks. All cases were categorized by RTOG scale of acute radiation dermatitis by Radiation Oncologist monitored during radiation.

Results: 154 patients was included in the study. Radiodermatitis was registered in 31 patients in HFRT arm (40,26%) respectively compared to 33 patient (42.85%) of patients in conventional treatment arm. Average age of the patients in the HFRT group was 58,72. Global estimate of health of the patients included in the study was 65,91.

Conclusion: Moderate hypofractionation now seem likely to become standard of breast cancer certainly shortening time and cost of the treatment, more convenient for the patients with good skin toxicity profile regarding incidence of acute radiodermatitis. Our single-institution analysis shows no significant difference of incidence of acute radiation dermatitis in women with breast cancer undergoing hypofractionated radiotherapy comparing to conventional fractionation regime.

Keywords: Acute radiodermatitis; hypofractionated radiotherapy, breast cancer

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2022**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

CIP – Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Matica srpske, Novi Sad

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (2022 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress,
November, 05-06 2022 Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula,
Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. - Novi Sad : Institut za
Onkologiju Vojvodine, 2022 (Novi Sad : NS digiprint).
– 56 str. : ilustr. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200.

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 78911241